

SAPIENZA
UNIVERSITÀ DI ROMA

MASTER DEGREE IN NATURAL SCIENCES

Accelerator Physics and Relativistic Electrodynamics

**Simulation for building a LINAC
using Astra**

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1 Introduction

This exercise is devoted to building a simplified version of a LINAC (Linear Accelerator), consisting of a cathode, a buncher, three solenoids, and an accelerating structure. Astra was used for the simulations and analysis conducted in this exercise.

2 Question and objective

Figure 1 shows the initial schematic of the LINAC, and the basic dimensions are also mentioned. However, the position of the accelerating structure was shifted forward during the exercise (will be explained later in 4.4).

Figure 1: Initial schematic diagram of the LINAC (given in the question).

The particles are tracked through the LINAC using Astra, which considers electromagnetic fields and beam dynamics effects like focusing and energy gain. The simulation results yield valuable information regarding beam characteristics, emittance growth, energy spread, and other relevant parameters.

The performance of the LINAC design is evaluated by analyzing the simulation results. The accelerator parameters are optimized to attain the desired beam quality, stability, and number of particles in the bunch after the RF cavity.

3 Goals of the experiment

The following can be realized as the goals of the exercise.

1. Particles bunch reaching the energy - 100 MeV.
2. Making the percentage of particles at the end of the LINAC higher than 50%.
3. Obtaining an emittance lower than 20 mm mrad.

4 Designing and intermediate results

4.1 Cathode

In a linear accelerator (LINAC), the cathode has the crucial role of generating electrons through a phenomenon known as thermionic emission. By subjecting the cathode to high temperatures, it undergoes electron emission, releasing electrons into the surrounding environment. These emitted electrons subsequently serve as the particle source for acceleration within the LINAC.

4.2 Buncher

The buncher is an essential component that plays a role in managing the longitudinal properties of the electron bunch. Its purpose is to shape the temporal structure of the bunch, ensuring that the electrons are appropriately spaced and synchronized for effective acceleration. Bunchers utilize electric fields, such as radiofrequency (RF) fields, to manipulate the bunch length and phase.

Initially, the buncher was fixed at 0.22m and its phase was determined as 266° using the scanning option (this value was selected to have the minimum RMS bunch

length) in Astra (See Figure 2).

Figure 2: The variation of RMS bunch length vs phase of the EM field in the buncher. The phase was determined as 266° to have the minimum RMS bunch length.

After the initialization of the buncher, the RMS bunch length was observed as shown in Figure 3. According to its behavior, it was determined that the accelerating cavity should be placed at 0.54m.

4.3 Solenoids

Solenoids, as magnetic elements employed in the LINAC, have the purpose of providing beam control and focusing. These devices generate a magnetic field along the beam path, enabling the manipulation of the electron beam by facilitating beam focusing, divergence control, and correction of beam emittance growth. Each solenoid within the LINAC may possess distinct field strengths, positions, and smoothing

Figure 3: The behavior of the RMS bunch length against the length (z) of the LINAC.

characteristics.

In order to find the maximum magnetic field of the first solenoid, first it was placed at 0.13 m and the behavior of the vertical RMS spot size against the maximum magnetic field was analyzed using the scanning function, as shown in Figure 4. The maximum magnetic field was determined as 0.025 T, which corresponds to the minimum vertical RMS spot size. The same procedure was repeated for the other two solenoids placed after the buncher.

4.4 Accelerating structure

The RF cavity, commonly referred to as the accelerating structure, assumes the vital role of accelerating the electron bunch during its traversal. With the resonant cavities, it generates an oscillating electric field that transfers energy to the electrons,

Figure 4: Variation of the vertical spot size vs the maximum of the B field for the first solenoid.

augmenting their velocity and kinetic energy.

As previously determined, the accelerating cavity was placed at 0.54 m. Then using the scanning option, the phase of the EM field was determined as 240° , to have the highest energy and the highest number of electrons (See Figure 5).

Figure 5: (Top): Average energy of the bunch vs the phase. (Bottom): The number of accelerated particles of the bunch vs the phase. Observing the two variations, the phase of the EM field was determined as 240° .

5 Final results

5.1 Schematic diagram of the LINAC

The final schematic of the LINAC with its specifics can be seen in Figure 6.

Figure 6: The final schematic diagram of the LINAC. The distance from the cathode to each component and its specific details are also mentioned.

5.2 Transverse emittance

Transverse emittance quantifies the beam quality by capturing the extent to which particles disperse in both position and momentum. Figure 7 shows that the transverse emittance is lower than 2 mrad mm on average. A decrease in emittance signifies a beam that is more precisely concentrated, resulting in a reduction in beam size and divergence. This enhanced focus enables improved management and confinement of the particle beam.

5.3 RMS beam size

The RMS beam size represents the spatial distribution of particles in the beam, reflecting its level of dispersion. Figure 8 shows that the RMS beam size is lower

Figure 7: The variation of the transverse emittance against the distance (z). On average, the transverse emittance is lower than 2 mrad mm .

than 0.5 mm on average. A smaller RMS beam size shows a more tightly packed and less scattered beam which enhances the beam quality. This focused and well-defined beam enables precise targeting and minimizes undesired interactions with accelerator walls.

5.4 Energy gain

Figure 9 shows the average energy of the particle bunch over distance. Particles coming from the cathode at an energy value of 0.09 MeV are accelerated to a maximum energy of 34.61 MeV . Within the RF cavity, the energy gradient was determined as 11.54 MeV/m .

Figure 8: The variation of the RMS beam size against the distance (z). On average, the RMS beam size is lower than 0.5 mm .

5.5 Number of particles

The simulation involved a stack of 100,000 particles (electrons), and following the passage through the accelerating cavity, it was observed that 96,034 particles remained active, representing a percentage of 96%. It indicates that a significant majority of the initial particles remained active and successfully underwent acceleration.

5.6 Longitudinal phase space

Figure 10 shows the longitudinal phase space of the particle bunch. The longitudinal phase space plays a vital role in the design of a linear accelerator (LINAC) by providing insights into the energy distribution of particles along the beam axis. Additionally, it is crucial for the effective compression of the particle beam into compact

Figure 9: The variation of the average particle energy against the distance (z).

bunches.

Figure 10: The longitudinal phase space of the particle bunch.

5.7 Front, top, and side view of the particle bunch

Figure 11 shows the front, top, and side views of the particle bunch traveling through the LINAC.

Figure 11: The front, top, and side views of the particle bunch traveling through the LINAC.